

Technical requirements for ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms

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Applicability of the document

These technical requirements apply to ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms.

Acronyms

- ACTRIS - Aerosol, Clouds and Trace gases Research InfraStructure
- ACTRIS GA – ACTRIS General Assembly
- ARES – Aerosol Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre
- ARS – Aerosol Remote Sensing
- CARPORT – CARS workflow management portal
- CARS - Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing
- CLU – Cloud Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre
- CCRES - Centre for Cloud Remote Sensing
- DC – Data Centre
- MP – Mobile Platform
- NF - National Facility
- NRT – Near-real time (less than 3 days from the measurements)
- OP – Observational Platform
- PI – Principal Investigator
- RI Comm – Research Infrastructure Committee
- RRT – Real-real time (less than 3 hours form the measurement)
- SCC – Single Calculus Chain

Reference documents

1. [Documentation on technical concepts and requirements for ACTRIS Observational Platforms](#)
2. [ACTRIS NF Labelling Plan](#)
3. [Descriptions of the workflows between ACTRIS components](#)
4. [ACTRIS Data Management Plan](#)
5. [CARS implementation plan](#)
6. [ACTRIS vocabulary](#)
7. Guidelines for EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations to access QA services
8. Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments
9. Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars
10. Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers
11. Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
12. Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer
13. Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars
14. Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer

1 Introduction

Aerosol remote sensing instruments as considered by ACTRIS are:

- a) aerosol high-power lidars;
- b) automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers;
- c) automatic low-power lidars and ceilometers.

ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing National Facilities operate aerosol high-power lidars and automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers.

Note: The technical requirements in this document do not apply to automatic low-power lidars / ceilometers which are currently operated as part of the ACTRIS Cloud Remote Sensing National Facilities

ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing National Facilities operate aerosol remote sensing instruments either as Observational Platforms (at fixed site) or as part of a Mobile Platform (movable).

In order to be labelled as **ACTRIS National Facility**, both the Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms, and the Mobile Platforms operating aerosol remote sensing instruments must undergo the labelling process. The labelling process is described in [Labelling of the ACTRIS National Facilities operating Aerosol Remote Sensing instruments](#)

Note: The technical requirements in this document do not apply to ACTRIS Mobile Platforms embedding aerosol remote sensing instruments

Aerosol remote sensing instruments can also be operated by the EARLINET (aerosol high-power lidars), AERONET (automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers) and E-PROFILE (automatic low-power lidars and ceilometers).

Note: The technical requirements in this document do not apply to EARLINET, AERONET and E-PROFILE stations which are not part of ACTRIS.

This document describes the requirements for the facility and the instruments, to be fulfilled by the **ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms**.

- General requirements for the facility are described in [Section 2](#).
- Technical requirements for the instruments are presented in [Section 3.1](#) and [Section 0](#).
- Technical requirements related to the measurements Quality Assurance are summarized [Section 3.2](#) and [Section 4.2](#). Details can be found in instrument-specific *Standard Operation Procedures* and in instrument-specific *Quality Assurance Procedures*.
- Things to consider when purchasing a new lidar are presented in [Annex 1](#).

2 General considerations

2.1 Principles applicable to ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing measurements

ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms must comply with the following principles:

Principle 1: The facility must comply with the general requirements

Principle 2: The lidar and the photometer must comply with the specific technical requirements.

Principle 3: The protocols for operation, measurement and quality assurance issued by of the Centre for Aerosol Remote Sensing (CARS) and the Aerosol Remote Sensing unit of the ACTRIS Data Centre (ARES) must be applied. If available, calibration and quality assurance tools approved by CARS must be implemented at the National Facility.

Principle 4: Participation of the National Facility to QA/QC activities scheduled by CARS is mandatory. In addition, and if necessary, CARS may schedule direct comparisons, site audits, training sessions and/or other actions.

Principle 5: Measurements and data workflow recommended by CARS & ARES must be followed. The National Facility has the responsibility to securely and permanently store and archive native data from the instruments and Level 0 data (raw data in the format to be submitted to the DC units). In order to guarantee secure store and archive of such data, the National Facilities should organize their archive in two different physical locations.

2.2 General requirements for the facility

The minimum setup of an ACTRIS aerosol remote-sensing station consists of a one-wavelength Raman with polarization discrimination capability, and a sun/sky photometer.

The optimum setup of an ACTRIS aerosol remote-sensing station consists of a three-wavelength Raman or high spectral resolution lidar with polarization discrimination capability and an automatic sun/sky and moon photometer (optionally also polarized) according to ACTRIS/AERONET standards, both operating continuously.

In order to be evaluated as technically compliant, an Aerosol Remote Sensing must fulfill the following requirements:

1) Synergy requirements

An ACTRIS Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platform should operate an aerosol high-power lidar and an automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer. These instruments should be collocated, i.e. situated in the same mixed layer in order to measure the same atmosphere. **The maximum allowed horizontal distance is 1 km.** Although not mandatory, it is advisable that the Aerosol Remote Sensing Observational Platforms also operate a collocated automatic low-power lidar / ceilometer.

2) Technical requirements for the aerosol high-power lidar

- a) The aerosol high-power lidar must fulfill at least the mandatory technical requirements described in [Section 3.1](#)
- b) The facility must implement the standard operating procedures as described in [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)

- c) The facility must implement the QA/QC procedures, as described in [Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
 - d) The facility must participate in the QA/QC actions scheduled by CARS, as summarized in [Section 3.2](#)
- 3) Technical requirements for the automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer**
- a) The automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer must fulfill at least the mandatory technical requirements described in [Section 0](#).
 - b) The facility must implement the standard operating procedures as described in [Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer](#)
 - c) The facility must implement the QA/QC procedures, as described in [Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer](#)
 - d) The facility must participate in the QA/QC actions scheduled by CARS, as summarized in [Section 4.2](#)
- 4) Other requirements**
- a) The facility must implement the measurement guidelines for the aerosol high-power lidar, as described in [Measurement Guidelines for aerosol high-power lidars](#)
 - b) The facility must implement the measurement guidelines for the automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer, as described in [Measurement Guidelines for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers](#)

3 Technical requirements for the aerosol high-power lidars

The following technical requirements apply to ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing National Facilities and to EARLINET-ACTRIS associated stations.

Measurements of aerosol extinction, backscatter and depolarization-ratio profiles are to be performed at least at one wavelength, either 355 or 532 nm.

3.1 Technical requirements for the instrument

Technical system parameters such as laser power, telescope aperture, receiver bandwidth and data acquisition system must be chosen such that profiles can be acquired throughout the troposphere up to the lower stratosphere with the required accuracy and temporal and spatial resolution. A separate near-range receiving system is recommended for observations in the lower planetary boundary layer. Configurations may vary to account for climatic circumstances, e.g., the typical height of the boundary layer for the location of the NF.

Tab. 1 Summary of mandatory and recommended technical requirements

Parameter	Mandatory (minimum requirements)	Recommended (optimum requirements)
Channels	$1\beta + 1\alpha + 1\delta$ at 355 nm or $1\beta + 1\alpha + 1\delta$ at 532 nm	$1\beta + 1\alpha + 1\delta$ at 355 nm and $1\beta + 1\alpha + 1\delta$ at 532 nm and 1β at 1064 nm
Height resolution raw (recorded signal)	≤ 15 m	≤ 3.75 m
Time resolution raw (recorded signal)	≤ 60 s	≤ 10 s
Full overlap (m)	$\leq 300^1$	≤ 200
Minimum altitude range of the 355 raw signal (to be obtained in defined conditions , see below)	≥ 15 km	
Minimum altitude range of the 532 raw signal (to be obtained in defined conditions , see below)	≥ 15 km	
Minimum altitude range of the 1064 raw signal (to be obtained in defined conditions , see below)	≥ 10 km	
Features	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Laser alignment (alignment camera²) ● Polarisation calibration ● Telecover ● Dark signal measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Unattended operation ● Automatic laser alignment ● Automatic polarization calibration

¹ This value must be reached in max. 5 years form the initial acceptance, for at least one couple of elastic and Raman channels. The applicability of the overlap correction will be investigated.

² Only if the assembly of a camera is not possible, alternative “online” control mechanisms for the laser alignment can be approved after verification by CARS.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Photodetector eye piece³ ● Pretrigger $\geq 20 \mu\text{s}$ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Automatic telecover ● Automatic dark signal measurement ● Photodetector eye piece ● Pretrigger $\geq 20 \mu\text{s}$ ● Temperature and humidity control ● Lidar status control ● Eye safety (automatic shut-down)
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Defined conditions for which the minimum altitude range of the raw signals must be obtained:

With clean air in the far range and an averaging time 1 hour:

- for 355 and 532 nm with aerosol OD 0.4 in the lower troposphere and a range resolution of 250 m, the SNR in the cross and parallel channels, respectively, must be:
 - 355 nm: SNR ≥ 17 (cross) and ≥ 65 (parallel) at 15 km;
 - 532 nm: SNR ≥ 11 (cross) and ≥ 55 (parallel) at 15 km;
- for 1064 nm with aerosol OD 0.13 in the lower troposphere and a range resolution of 500 m the SNR in the total signal must be: SNR ≥ 9 at 10 Km.

Recommendations for purchase of aerosol high-power lidars are provided in [Annex 1](#).

3.2 Requirements related to the Quality Assurance of the measurements

Quality control of the aerosol high-power lidar Level 0 data is in the responsibility of the instrument operator, with the support of CARS. ACTRIS high-power aerosol lidars should apply specific calibration and quality assurance measures and tools. Quality assurance measures for aerosol lidars include internal and external check-ups.

External check-ups refer to:

1. **Direct comparison with a reference lidar systems operated by CARS.** Intercomparison measurements with one of the reference lidar systems shall be performed for new systems and after major upgrades if CARS resources allow it.
2. **Analysis of the QA tests by CARS.** The QA tests will be analyzed regularly by CARS experts in order to check and approve the instrument configuration in the Single Calculus Chain (SCC). QA tests to be performed by the operator and reported to CARS are:

Tab. 2 Mandatory Quality Assurance tests to be submitted to CARS:

QA test	Purpose	Periodicity for reporting
Telecover	test optical alignment	Once per year AND Each time the lidar is moved AND

³ Alternative methods to overcome the sensitivity inhomogeneity of the photodetectors can be approved after verification by CARS.

		Each time significant hardware interventions are done to the instrument
Rayleigh fit	test optical alignment	Once per year AND Each time the lidar is moved AND Each time significant hardware interventions are done to the instrument
Polarization calibration	calibration	Each time the lidar is moved AND Each time significant hardware interventions are done to the instrument
Zero bin test	electronic synchronization	Once AND Each time significant hardware interventions are done to the instrument
Dark signal measurement	electronic distortion subtraction	Once AND Each time significant hardware interventions are done to the instrument

3. **Site audits.** Site audits will be scheduled and performed by CARS for new National Facilities and/or in case of persistent instrumental problems.

Internal check-ups refer to:

1. **Regular performance of the QA tests.** Operators are advised to perform the QA tests (see Tab. 2) as often as possible but at least monthly, and check the instrument's performance over time.
2. **Implementation and use of the QA/QC tools approved by CARS.** Specific tools developed by CARS can be downloaded from CARS website. These tools have to be applied regularly based on the recommendations and under the supervision of CARS.

Details referring to the QA/QC of the measurements are described in [Quality Assurance Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#).

Details referring to the operation of the instrument are described in [Standard Operation Procedure for aerosol high-power lidars](#).

4 Technical requirements for the automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer

The following technical requirements apply to ACTRIS aerosol remote sensing National Facilities and to AERONET-ACTRIS associated stations.

4.1 Technical requirements for the instrument

Instrument observation capability

For columnar aerosol measurements, the required instrument is a fully automatic sun/sky photometer including the direct-moon extinction measurement capability.

Spectral AOD (day and night) and downward angular atmospheric radiance measurements (also called sky radiance) are mandatory. In addition, sky angular polarization measurements can provide the full picture of the radiation characteristics, but remain optional. Direct sun/moon and sky radiance measurements follow a consistent scheduled scenario.

Two versions of automatic sun/sky/lunar photometers can be considered,

- Cimel 318T Standard model, basically equipped with the 9 the following spectral filters (CWL/BW: 340/2, 380/4, 440/10, 500/10, 675/10, 870/10, 937/10, 1020/10, 1640/25 nm)
- Cimel 318P Polarized model, performing additional sky polarization measurements at the same wavelength as the standard model. It should be noted that this instrument performed much more measurements which take more time and need more energy.

Instrument setup conditions

Clear field of view with a maximum 10° elevation mask in all the directions is requested. South ways not obstructed.

Data transfer and communications

It is mandatory that the data are transferred regularly (no more than 1h after acquisition) to the ASP/AERONET units in charge of Quality Control and Assurance. For this purpose, several transmission channels may be used like RS232 (with USB adaptor) to connect to computer (100 m line max), USB for local and temporary connection to a laptop, GPRS to transfer data to the network FTP with Sim Card, Satellite to transfer to the database via a transmitter to a geostationary satellite from EUMETSAT for example.

Data is typically transmitted via 2 channels. For a majority of sites, data is transmitted by either the software provided with the instrument or software developed by ASP/AERONET units running on a PC linked to the internet and to the photometer. In case of a very remote site far from the internet, a satellite transmitter is used, over Europe and Africa, through EUMETSAT channels. Data rate is however low which has impacts on the photometer polar and lunar versions having a too high data rate for this type of transmission).

Instrumental limitations and duty cycle

The instrument belonging to the user must benefit from recent technology progress and should not be older than 15 years.

To preserve observation continuity at his site during the calibration phase that may require about 2 months, an additional photometer head is necessary since the ASP/AERONET units cannot guarantee available spare instruments. ASP/AERONET units consider this as an investment to be done at the country level (mutualization of spare instruments).

4.2 Requirements related to the Quality Assurance of the measurements

ASP units are in charge of most of the quality control/assurance activities, by regularly following instrument status, detecting anomalies, informing users and solving problems. However, there are mandatory / recommended procedures to be followed by users.

Data Quality Monitoring Tools

All NF operators have free access to the monitoring webpage and can remotely check the status of their instrument (battery level, tracking system, humidity and temperature sensors, etc.). Users/Operators also have easy access to data in near real time, so that they can detect apparent calibration shifts due to collimator obstruction or similar issues.

Weekly Check procedures

The users and operators of NF are involved in the quality control process. The visual inspection of the instrument (optics, collimator and cables to solar panel and data transmission system) once a week is required. If users/operators are not following these protocols, data quantity and quality could be dramatically affected and quality assurance procedures will not allow the data to reach the QA assured data level in the database.

NF-CF interactions

To maximize the duty cycle of the instrument, users/operators are expected to be reactive on alerts sent by the CF corresponding units.

Calibration

Regular recalibration is mandatory and expected to be performed every 12 months on average. After the calibration, it is required to set the instrument up again as quickly as possible. To preserve observation continuity at his site during the calibration phase that may require a couple of months, an additional photometer head is necessary since the ASP/AERONET units cannot guarantee available spare instruments. ASP/AERONET units consider this as an investment to be done at the country level (mutualization of spare instruments).

Details referring to the QA/QC of the measurements are described in [Quality Assurance Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer](#).

Details referring to the operation of the instrument are described in [Standard Operation Procedure for automatic sun/sky/lunar photometer](#).

Annex 1. Things to consider when purchasing a new lidar

The fulfillment of the above requirements will be checked by CARS regularly through specific QA tests and, for the new or upgraded lidars, through direct comparison with a reference lidar if CARS resources allow it. In order to make sure that the lidar will be compliant when delivered, CARS advises the buyers to include the following requirements in the tendering documents, in addition to the technical specifications:

1) Proof of experience

The tender should include proof of the successful production of previous systems which had similar capabilities to the specified system and are compliant with ACTRIS requirements. The tender should also include references from two previous customers, preferably from other ACTRIS National Facilities.

2) System acceptance

The verification of the fulfilment of the specifications shall be carried out within the framework of a test plan to be coordinated by the Contractor with the Client in advance. Within the scope of this test plan, measurements of technical parameters shall be carried out by the Contractor and recorded. The acceptance will be divided into a Factory Acceptance Testing (FAT, at the Contractor site) and a Site Acceptance Testing (SAT, at the Client site).

The Contractor shall prepare corresponding test reports for FAT and SAT and make them available to the Client in due time. The test reports shall include the test data in the standard format defined by CARS.

The FAT procedure should contain continuous measurements (proved by quicklooks) during five consecutive days with QA tests (dark, telecover, Rayleigh-fit and polarisation calibration measurements) performed at every day and every night, and can be extended further up to a maximum of seven days in total, in case the environmental conditions are not favorable for the tests to be performed. The measurement data of the results of the FAT are to be handed over to the Client at least one month prior to the shipment. Within this timeframe, the Client may consult CARS for opinion. The Client will inform the Contractor about the acceptance not later than one month after the delivery of the FAT, and has the right to refuse the shipment in case the test results prove that the lidar is not compliant.

The SAT shall be carried out jointly by the Contractor and the Client during the installation on site and will last two days. A full set of QA tests has to be performed both at day and night, and immediately delivered to CARS for analysis. The Client has the right to refuse the deliverance in case the QA test results prove that the lidar is not compliant. The results are to be documented in a joint protocol.

Each QA-measurement set must comprise:

- Six consecutive five minute-averaged dark measurements of the analogue signals
- Telecover measurements with ten times NESW sector measurements of 30 second averages for each quadrant sector in order to decrease the influence of atmospheric changes.
- For coaxial lidar setups: Telecover measurements with ten times inner and outer ring sector measurements of 30 second averages for each sector in order to decrease the influence of atmospheric changes. Rayleigh-fit measurements with one hour average with an aerosol-free region of at least 1 km range at a minimum height of eight km.

- Polarisation calibration with an uncertainty of the polarisation calibration factor of 2% or less.
- Camera images of the laser beam alignment in the field-of-view stop of the telescope.

3) Relevant Standards and accreditations

The supplier shall maintain a Quality Management System in accordance with DIN EN ISO 9001.

4) Training

Training for up to four people will be provided at Lidar Installation site when the instrument is installed.

5) Force Majeure Event and hardship

Force Majeure shall be limited to one or more of the following events: hurricanes, tempest, acts of state or public enemy, wars, revolutions, uprisings, hostilities, civil disturbances, riots, civil war, pandemic like COVID-19, insurrection, and invasion. For the avoidance of doubt, strikes, lockouts and shutdowns of a Party (or of any person engaged by any of them) shall not be a force majeure event for that Party. Hardship Clause 2020 also applies.

6) User and Service Manuals

Electronic copies of full manuals for setup, operation, maintenance and software are required to be delivered latest with the delivery of the FAT.

Full specifications (paper or electronic) for all components, including optics, are required. These should include (besides the common lidar specifications):

- Laser beam divergence (full width) at the circle which includes 86% of the energy
- Trigger delays for analogue and photon-counting signals for all channels
- Dead time for all photon counting channels
- Telescope diameter, focal length and secondary mirror obscuration
- For each interference filter: interference filter centre wavelength, full-width-half-maximum bandwidth, full-width bandwidth at 90% of maximum, effective refractive index and out-of-band blocking (optical density and range over which that optical density applies)
- Manufacturer and type of the detectors with specifications from the manufacturer
- Nominal high voltage of the detectors (PMTs or APDs).
- Diattenuation of the receiver and transmitter optics with polarisation effects at the used wavelengths
- Degree of linear polarisation of the emitted laser beam at all wavelengths at which polarization measurements are performed.
- Rotation angle of the plane of the major axis of the laser polarisation (beta) with respect to the reference plane of the receiver optics, for which usually the incidence plane of the polarising beam splitter cube is used, at all wavelengths at which polarization measurements are performed
- Ellipticity of the laser polarisation (or the degree of circular polarisation).
- The measured expansion and polarization properties of the beam expanders
- Di-attenuation measurements for all the relevant optical components
- Optical ray-tracing of all the optical paths
- Dead time measurements for all the optical channels
- Laser polarization purity measurements for the transmitted beam at all wavelengths at which polarization measurements are performed, with details of measurement technique

Note: In case the lidar is provided in a container, the container must be IP66-rated, and the mechanical design drawings of the container layout must be provided. Lightning protection must be provided.

7) Warranty

Warranty of parts against partial or full failure for 2 years should be included, except for the laser and its components where 1 year is required. All components used must be brand new.

8) Service and spare parts

The instrument should be supplied with one set of spare flashlamps and a spare laser deioniser cartridge and water filter (if used). The cost of routine spare parts for future use should be detailed in the tender.

Prompt support and repair service must be committed by the Contractor, especially on-site support when repairs are required for which shipping of components to the supplier is impractical, or when repair or re-installation requires high skill levels or equipment knowledge, and free telephone and e-mail support during office hours. The tender should describe the services and conditions that are provided by the manufacturer.

9) Milestones (possibly related to payments)

- Delivery of the system design
- Delivery of the detailed specifications of the system (Handbook of Instrument)
- Delivery and acceptance of the FAT report
- Delivery of the system and provision of training
- Delivery and acceptance of the SAT report